

Maxims - Translational Analysis of Theresa May Speeches at the UN General Assembly into Arabic

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Abstract: Basically, euphemisms are words or phrases that talk indirectly about something unpleasant or offensive. This can be shown and explained through the analysis of euphemistic expressions found in political speeches. For now, we are going to explore the Theresa May's political speeches in order to indicate and highlight the importance of such phenomenon and how to analyze them by using pragmatic means. To put this differently, we can say how euphemistic expressions can hide a great message behind a kind expression or words.

الملخص

إن التعبيرات المملّفة هي كلمات أو عبارات تتحدث بشكل غير مباشر عن شيء غير سار أو مسيء. ويمكن إظهار ذلك وتفسيره من خلال تحليل التعبيرات المملّفة الموجودة في الخطاب السياسية. في الوقت الحالي، سنستكشف الخطاب السياسية لتيريزا ماي من أجل الإشارة إلى أهمية هذه الظاهرة وكيفية تحليلها باستخدام وسائل برجماتية. بعبارة أخرى، يمكننا أن نقول كيف يمكن للتعبيرات المملّفة أن تخفي رسالة عظيمة وراء تعبير أو كلمات لطيفة.

1. What is Euphemism?

Euphemism can be defined as a word or a phrase that is used to replace a taboo word (Fairman, 2009: 56), this definition came alongside many other definitions aim to provide an idea to what euphemism is. Geoffrey Leach also defined euphemism as the linguistic equivalent of disinfectant (1974: 53). The British George Blunt was the first who used euphemism in his *Glossophobia* (1656) and he defines it as “*a good or favorable interpretation of a bad word*”. In many languages, people avoid the use of certain words that are considered rude or taboo in some way and people still try to use them in a roundabout way, the substitution is known as euphemism (ibid).

Euphemism is described as being a powerful linguistic tool rooted deep inside our language and we use it unconsciously, and it is still used by those who claim to be proud plain speakers (Linfoot-Ham, 2005: 228). The need for euphemism is mandatory because it provides a safe environment to discuss taboo subjects without feeling embarrassed or insulting anyone, in other words, it is a form of civility (ibid).

In short, euphemism is a mask used to replace a word or a phrase by another word or phrase and express the same meaning that was originally expressed. The reason why euphemism is used can vary according to the subject of communication, whether it is a cultural, social, religious or political taboo (www.fictionwriting.about.com).

Euphemism is not a new comer to English, since people always needed to maintain smooth social relations with each other in various subjects of everyday communication, for example, it was very normal to people to talk about the (Upper- Class) in Britain as a custom of everyday communication, but today the situation is different due to the social changes that took place in the British society, so it is referred to as the (U and non-U) since it is considered a sensitive issue to the people of genteel middle classes (Lyons, 1981: 150).

The strong connection became clear between euphemism and sociolinguistics due to the fact that euphemism is a tool used by the society to avoid being exposed to the use of one of the (Tabooed)

or the socially abandoned words (Four-Letter words). The avoidance of such words affects and preserves the social meanings and the expressiveness of the uttered message without distorting the meaning of the message with taboo words (Lyons, 1981: 151).

It is obvious that euphemism helps language users to understand the meaning of the words. Linguists agreed that the meaning of the words found in the dictionary is not the only meaning of that word, and the word can indicate various meaning if used in different contexts, i.e. the meaning of the word is not constative but flexible (ibid).

According to the Oxford Companion to the English Language, the meaning of euphemism is “*a word or a phrase is considered a polite replacement for another word or a phrase, which is impolite, offensive or vulgar or offensive to a certain religious group*” (1992).

2. Euphemism of Sociolinguistics

The concept of sociolinguistics can be understood by studying the relationship between language and society, and why we change the language register while we communicate in different social events. It can be said that it studies the functions of language in society, and how people use it to convey sentences that are rich with information and expresses the social relationships in society, and how people use language to express different aspects of various social identities by using language (Holmes, 2017: 1).

Language users found techniques to avoid discussing certain subjects and talk about them in an indirect and roundabout way, since they consider language as a medium of communication used by people to convey their thoughts and ideas, and there are different cultural meanings that are conveyed through the use of language, but there are subjects that should not be said out aloud in every culture. Euphemism, as a language filter, is used to talk about certain sensitive subjects indirectly. In order to consider a certain subject tabooed, it has to be sensitive or harmful to a certain group in any society that causes them anxiety, shame and embarrassment. In sociolinguistics, euphemism is an aspect of politeness principle that functions as a language constrain, and the lineaments of euphemism rise when there are certain subjects can only be referred to euphemistically and in certain circumstances (Wardhaugh, 2011: 238-239).

In every society, there are always movements of “free speech”, i.e. those who claim to be free speakers and break all the boundaries imposed by the society in an attempt to break the taboo subjects as a form of rebellion on the social boundaries (ibid).

Tabooed subjects differ in their intensity from one culture to another, but they range between subjects that are known to be sensitive in every society like (politics, religious matters, sex, death, or bodily functions). English, like any other language, has its own tabooed subjects, and English speakers know that there are rules that should never be broken and lines should never be crossed.

3. Euphemism and Political Correctness

The use of political correctness requires a higher degree of precision in the use of language, since the language used in political events needs to summon the excellency of the speaker and whom he represents. The accuracy in the terminology is somehow a good sign of PC, like the use of (*chairperson*) instead of (*chairman*) because it can also be a (*chairwoman*) and that summons a degree of language awareness. Another idea about the nature of PC can be in fact that people like to be called by the name they represent, take the example of (*married*), which can be defined as the relationship between two people of the opposite sex and the legal marriage cannot be concluded unless the two parties are in a heterosexual relationship, but using the term (*partner*) may also indicates that the couple are (*gay*) or (*lesbian*) and that's why the use of married are more preferable (Burridge, 2006:459).

The relationship between euphemism and PC is that PC exists in the behavior of the euphemistic language, and came as a result from the collapsation of the euphemistic language. A lot of people consider euphemism as the disadvantageous mark that language carries to shade what was originally meant and to ruin inconvenient facts. Euphemism, with the progress every society made, seems to

control the social discourse, but after all it resorts to the fact that euphemism is a frontline shield that separates what is said from what is meant from the unpleasant realities, in other words, in PC, euphemism is a (double-edged sword) applied by both supporters and critics to support their senior positions (ibid).

According to Mulder and Banks, if you are replying to people softly, this means that you are of high infirmity and sensitivity in using your language taking into consideration your position comparing to others. Those who stand against the concept of PC, see that it is fool to think that saying a nice thing will produce a nicer world, because it will deviate people and what was meant in the first place, and, in the end, it is no more than euphemism (1996: 34).

The fact that finding a different word carries the same meaning depends highly on the context, since the language of the PC is both euphemistic and dysphemistic because this is how things work in the world of politics (ibid).

4. Types of Euphemism

Kaosa-Ad (2009) divided the types of euphemism into five types, and each has its own classifications (2009:15-21).

1. Shortening: it is divided into five types:

- a) Abbreviation: according to Meyer, abbreviation is formed by combining the first letters of two (or more) words to form a new word, (S.O.B= son of a bitch) (2009:181).
- b) Backformation: according to Fromkin, back formation is a word formed by omitting affixes, (burglar = burgle) (2003:97).
- c) Diminutive: according to Kaosa-Ad, diminutive can be done by adding a suffix and shortening the word at the same time, these suffixes are (-kins, -ie, -y, etc.), (hind end = buttock) (2009:16).
- d) Omission: this type of shortening is done by omitting letters and replace them with dashes, (bi*ch) (ibid).
- e) Clipping: it can be defined as deleting parts of the words, (nation = damnation) or (gee= Jesus) (ibid).

2. Circumlocution: this type of euphemism is known to be a phonological modification, which employ many words to explain a meaning that has been widening, (postconsumer secondary material = garbage) (Allen & Burrige, 2006:128).

3. Remodeling: remodeling is divided into three types:

- a) Phonological distortion: it is the case where language speakers change the original pronunciation, (heck = hell) (Burrige, 2005: 125).
- b) Blending: this type of remodeling is done by combing two words (or more) to form a completely new word, and some parts of the two blended words might be deleted, (God rot = drat) (Kaosa-Ad, 2009:17).
- c) Reduplication: Booij explained that reduplication is the repetition of letters or syllables, (Jesus Christ = jeepers creepers) (2007: 35).

4. Semantic changes: semantic changes are divided into three types as follows:

- a) Semantic shifts: it is divided into two main types:
 - General-for-specific: uses a general term or expression instead of a more specific taboo one, like shifting the focus from the specific body part to a general one (chest = breasts).
 - Part-for-whole: uses a part to describe the whole, (we spend a penny = go to the lavatory) (Koasa- Ad, 2009: 17).

- b) Metaphorical transfer: combining a taboo topic with another with a pleasurable notion, i.e. it can be established, or at the same time, it can be figurative, (old age = twilight years) (Prayogi, 2008: 8).
- c) Elevation: it is the process by which the speaker replaces a taboo word with another that carries a more pleasing indication (standard = average) (Kaosa-Ad, 2009:20).

5. Borrowing: it is divided into two types:

- a) Internal borrowing: it is the process of borrowing from sub-languages, (luectic disease = syphilis).
- b) External borrowing: it can be defined as the use of words that are borrowed from other languages to function as euphemisms in the receptor language, and we can consider French and Latin as good providers to English, (perspire = sweat) (Kaosa-Ad, 2009:20).

5. Euphemism and Taboo

The word taboo first rose near the end of the eighteenth century, and it was derived from the Tongan (*tabu*), and it means (to forbid) or (forbidden). As a language filter, it can be imposed on any type of forbiddance. It is highly appreciated in any society, since it is considered a form of etiquette, or a line that should never be crossed by adults or children, and it helps the parents to raise their children properly, and never misbehave under any circumstance (Radcliffe, 1939: 5).

Many refer to the word taboo as a word of extensive significance, since it not only refers to words, but many other actions that differ from one society to another. It can refer to a human sacrifice, a thing that should never be eaten, or to a human action that is sanctioned by the traditions or the law itself (Cook, 1967: 176).

According to Cook, taboo can be applied over places that should never be entered or food that should never be eaten, or even actions that should never be done. These taboos are universals, since every culture is unique with what it carries under the folds of centuries it survived from. Some taboos are religious based, for instance, Muslims do not eat meat unless it is Halal, Jews fast at Passover, and Muslims fast during Ramadan (ibid).

There is a strong and intimate relationship between taboo and euphemism, and that deep relation rises from the fact that the function of euphemism covers the hideous effect caused by taboo words, i.e. it makes taboo more acceptable. The application of euphemism to serve this purpose is not bizarre, since euphemism served as a mask to cover the ugliness of human bad expressions since the ancient Athenian ages where people used to call inappropriate expressions with temperate and more acceptable terms that needed the use of euphemism, like calling a prison (chamber). In different context, taboo is considered stimuli to euphemism (Fromakin, 2003:479).

6. Political Euphemism and Discourse

In order to identify the relation between politics and euphemism, we need to define the concept of political discourse. The word discourse originally means (an argument) and it is of Latin origin, this type of argument usually carries the nature of laying an idea on the table of discussion. Discourse is a way of using language as a mean of social communication, which can also be considered as an event of interaction that carries the nature of social status (Van Dijk, 1997, 2).

Van Dijk believes that language of discourse is not used by everybody, for there are certain factors that need to be taken into consideration like time, place, the status of the speaker, the reason behind saying certain words, and the right time to say something (ibid).

As Fairclough stated, the meaning of discourse, especially in politics, can include the meaning that occurs beyond the literal and syntactic meanings of the expression, i.e. it includes the discourse in which people discuss their ideologies and different practices through inexplicit expressions (1989:24).

In simpler terms, discourse is meant to analyze the meaning of expressions that people use to convey what they mean to employ it in their social interaction and use it to enjoy the advantage of power provided by words that indicate authority and influence. The analysis can take a written form like diaries, laws, letters and contracts, or an oral form like songs, interviews, poetry, meetings, discussions, and news (Van Dijk, 1981).

Political discourse is inclusive to some point due to the fact that it discusses the systematic methods of subject matters. Despite that, it is important to give a closer observation to what is meant by Political Discourse (PD), and the nature of the term. Shiffrin and Tannen (2001) stated that “*political discourse is a discourse which is itself political*”. They also gave another definition of PD as “*An analysis of political discourse is simply an example of discourse type, without explicit reference to political content or political context*” (2001: 398).

Along history, it is hard to find a political speech that is free from the use of euphemism, since those who are ready to go out and narrate a speech are fully equipped with a list of euphemisms, without which it is hard to survive that speech. There are euphemisms that gained the approval of many, especially in the political field, and have strong connection with the norms of Political Correctness, like it has been discussed before, these euphemism sometimes are dedicated to some political-tribal membership, at the same time, they are used to, for example, convince the majority to vote and elect a president. Language changes with time, and so does euphemism, that change must match the needs of human, and the political need comes on the top of other needs. This change is referred to by Steven Pinker as the (Euphemism Treadmill), which is defined by Urban Dictionary as “*The process by which a pejorative term is replaced by a more politically correct term, only to over time be corrupted and used pejoratively itself until a new term is introduced, upon which the cycle repeats itself*” (www.urbandictionary.com). Steven Pinker argues that this lead the treadmill to be inability to step off, since, as he thought, replacing the old terms with new ones is motivated by the untruthful theory that language is the main influencer of thoughts (www.cato.org).

7. Advantages and Disadvantages of Euphemism

The advantages and disadvantages of euphemism are obvious in many fields, especially media, so it is important to highlight the need of euphemism in this field, whether in spoken or written form. Some politicians use euphemism on purpose in their campaigns to attract the attention of people and voters, while others do not use euphemisms for many reasons.

The reason why some politicians refine from using euphemism is because it is a bauble-edged-sword, i.e. it has advantages and disadvantages. Since language is a sign of power, politicians tend to monopolize the meaning by smoothing it, and give it a form of legitimating (Rahardjo, 2002: 135).

The loss of face is one of the main reasons behind using euphemism by politicians in order to maintain a good image in front of their rivals. According to Rusman, he stated that without lying, life cannot go smoothly and it becomes intolerable, especially in politics, since it is a game played by the leaders of the world (2000: 48).

Some think of euphemism as a perfume, in other words, it is like the bad truth that wears expensive cologne to cover its ugly reality. The same thing applies on politicians who lie about their inner intentions, since euphemism is a mask that covers the crude and harmful expressions, otherwise, conflicts will rage because of an offensive expression has been said that triggers an influential personeel. This leads to the fact that euphemism is a game of semantics to avoid saying what is really meant, which leads to one of the disadvantages which displays euphemism as being misleading and dishonest semantic device in conveying the ugly truth of reality. One more disadvantage is that it is forbidden in academic writing because it demands honesty and objectiveness in the content without disguising realities (Holder, 2008).

Not all euphemisms are harmful some of them protect against serious harm. Euphemisms, like words and phrases, come in different shapes and sizes, and used according to a plan in the head of

the speaker, i.e. u need to be intentional in the use of euphemism and confident that it will serve the purpose of its use (www.thoughtco.com).

A good example of the advantage of euphemistic is when it is being used to comfort. Comfort is used to reduce tension and make those who are having a conversation feel more comfortable and relaxed. For instance, if someone is having a conversation with a person who has lost his mother recently, it is better to say “passed away” instead of “died” since the influence of the taboo is less harmful in the first one (Keyes, 2010). One of the disadvantages is disguise that is produced sometimes by the use of euphemism; in that case it produces disorientation to others.

8. Euphemism and Dysphemism

In their book “*Euphemism and Dysphemism*”, Allen and Burrige defined dysphemism as “*an expression with connotations that are offensive either about the denotatum or to the audience, or both, and it is substituted for a natural or euphemistic expression for just that reason*” (1991:26).

Unlike euphemism, dysphemism is used to talk about a negative matter, like talking about an opponent or things that someone talks about to show despair. Dysphemism is used highly in politics and considered a political characteristic, like when feminist talk about men, or when two election candidates go through a debate (ibid).

Euphemism and dysphemism are pretty much alike, but there are two characterized differences between them:

- Part for Whole Dysphemism (Synecdoche): it is used more frequently than the other types, which employs a part to describe the whole, like when someone describes a revolution by mentioning the leader (one person to describe the entire action).
- Hyperbole and Understatement: it is the antithesis or the opposite between hyperbole and understatement is inappropriate. Hyperbole is used to exaggerate an offense, example: (pea brain). Understatement is used when, for example, someone is waiting for two people to finish their conversation and say (if you could just spare me a FEW moments of your time)... here the speaker stresses on (FEW) to underestimate the importance on their action.

Dysphemism is mainly used in small or personal disputes and the insults vary according to the situation, and they include:

1. “*Comparisons of people to animals*”: it is some sort of ascription of someone to an animal based on their look or behavior (ex: mouse, bitch, dog, etc) (Allan and Burrige, 1991: 26).
2. “*Epithets derived from tabooed bodily organs or bodily effluvia*” (ex: stinky) (ibid).
3. “*Ascriptions of mental or physical inadequacy*” i.e. describing someone not stable by calling him\her (idiot), (airhead), (moron), etc. It can also describe a body part like (four-eyes), (spastic), etc. (ibid).
4. Terms of disrespect or slurs that offend the character of the opponent, like (bidly), (bag), (crank), etc. (Allen and Burrige, 1991:27-28).

Dysphemism is not always used as an insult, some people employ offensive expressions to be used humorously or just to tease someone, like when a group of friends come up with nick names to each other (ibid).

There is a similarity between euphemism and dysphemism which is the interaction with the style. In the case of dysphemism, it creates stylistic discord, like when someone shouts an inappropriate word or sentence in a formal occasion (ibid).

9. Euphemism in Translational Perspective

There is a common consensus among translation and translation theorist that translation is merely an act of communication between two parties. The source text departs from its culture to nest on the

culture of the target text. The departure of the text is accompanied by number of transformations involves the meaning and its social and linguistic manifestations.

The whole process of translation is tainted by the conflict of whether to take the (form) or (content) as the main priority. Amidst this chaos, euphemisms come as a phenomenon that the translator needs to pay special attention to, cause the ignoring of which will result in distorting the level of politeness the original writer intended to have in his work.

10. The Analysis of Theresa May Speeches: The Model of Leech's Politeness Maxims

Politeness principle is considered one of the main elements that fulfill the conditions must be present to have social interaction. Geoffrey Leech defines politeness as *"forms of behavior that establish and maintain feelings of comity within the social group, that is the ability of the participants in a social interaction to engage the interaction in an atmosphere of relative harmony. It can be expressed by certain polite formulaic utterances like please, thank you, excuse me, sorry, etc"* (Leech, 1983). The awareness of the politeness principle is a major prerequisite to reach an appropriate degree of courtesy must exist to maintain a good social appearance. Courtesy can be seen from different angles, and the most important one is having it in communication as in politeness language. Politeness, in this perspective is viewed as a reflection to beautifully the communication in the verbal or speaking manner. At this level, there is what is known as (word choice) on different levels (grammar, sentence, or intonation), here; it is the time when the level of politeness affects the linguistic politeness to maintain smooth interaction (danks84.wordpress.com).

1. *"it is a great honor for me to address this General Assembly for the first time and to do so as Prime Minister"*

"إنه لشرف كبير لي أن أخطب هذه الجمعية العامة للمرة الأولى، وأن أفعل ذلك بوصفي رئيسة وزراء"

The Praise Maxim/ The Modesty Maxim: The former PM of the United Kingdom started her first speech as the Prime Minister at the General Assembly of the UN by maximizing Praise of the hearer and minimizes praise to self. This statement is of two maxims; the first maxim is praise maxim where she minimizes praise of self while maximizing praise of the hearer, while the second part expresses the modesty of Theresa towards herself and stating such a humble expression although she is the PM of one of the strongest countries of the world. This euphemistic expression falls under the category of semantic innovation of overstatement to show to lengthen the title of the situation. The translation is clearly of a literal nature since the translator dedicated his words to serve the source text and transfer the nature of the source culture to the target reader.

"We gather here today because we know that such challenges do not respect the borders of our individual nations and that only by working together shall we overcome them."

"ونحن نلتقي هنا اليوم لأننا نعلم بأن تحديات كهذه لا تحترم حدود أي من دولنا، وأن لا يمكن لنا التغلب عليها إلا بالعمل معاً"

The Agreement Maxim: countries around the world are facing unprecedented threats that disturbs the international order and these countries try to stabilize the situation as much as possible, Theresa here is stressing on the common opinion of these threats that summons the agreement maxim as all the countries are suffering from destabilizations that sour the safety and stability of their nations. Theresa here maximizes the agreement due to the fact that these threats are on international scale and they are getting under the skin of many strong nations. This overstatement has a long title but short message (we need to work together to stop them). The translator appears to be loyal to the source text and transferred the message exactly how Theresa delivered it, on the other hand, the message does not harm the Arab society since they are also suffering from terrorism themselves.

"We will continue to honor our commitment to spend 0.7% of our Gross National Income on development, building on the achievements we have already made to reduce poverty, deal with instability and increase prosperity the world over. And we will drive forward the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals".

"سواصل الوفاء بالتزامنا بإنفاق 0.7% من دخلنا القومي الإجمالي على التنمية، والبناء على الإنجازات التي حققناها فعلا لخفض نسبة الفقر، ومعالجة عدم الاستقرار ورفع مستوى الازدهار في العالم أجمع. وسندفع قُدماً باتجاه تطبيق أهداف التنمية المستدامة".

The Generosity Maxim: Theresa May stresses in her speech on the commitment that the UK will continue to spend 0.7% of GNI of the UK that will maximize the cost on the country to maximize benefit to the rest of the world at the same time. This generosity stems from the consideration to the rest of the world that every individual must live a decent life where the governments care for the basic needs of every human being. It is another overstatement that falls under the semantic innovation where the speaker (narrates) the accomplishments one by one to express the results of his doings. The translator was keen to transfer the original expression to the target receiver with high accuracy, but it is worthy to note here that the political nature of the expression did not give the translator much of freedom to be creative.

"We will continue to champion the rights of women and girls, making sure that all girls get the education they deserve, and tackling horrific abuses such as female genital mutilation and the use of sexual violence in conflict".

"كما سنستمر في المناداة بحقوق النساء والفتيات، وضمان حصول جميع الفتيات على التعليم الذي يستحقه، ومعالجة الانتهاكات المروعة كختان الإناث واللجوء إلى العنف الجنسي في الصراع"

The Sympathy Maxim: the UK is one of the countries that are known to be patronage to women's rights and called to gender equality (www.equalityhumanrights.com), and that makes it clear why the former PM called to defend women's right at the UN and sympathizing with females, especially in conflict countries, like Somalia, Syria and south Sudan by maximizing sympathy towards them. The semantic innovation represented itself under the category of overstatement where the expression is long to express the gravity of event and action. The translation is also of a literal nature.

"It is an unprecedented figure, one that has almost doubled in a decade. And yet UN appeals are underfunded; host countries are not getting enough support; and refugees are not getting the aid, education and economic opportunities they need."

"إنه رقم لم يسبق له مثيل؛ رقم تضاعف خلال العقد الأخير. ومع ذلك ما زال هناك عجز في تمويل نداءات الأمم المتحدة؛ والدول المضيفة لا تحصل على الدعم الكافي؛ واللاجئون لا يحصلون على المساعدة والتعليم والفرص الاقتصادية التي يحتاجون اليه"

The Consideration Maxim/ The Modesty Maxim: this expression is divided into two parts; the first part is of consideration maxim where Theresa is minimizing the hearers discomfort or displeasure by delivering the idea that they are not neglected and their case is being discussed on international scale, the second part is of modesty maxim, Theresa is maximizing the dispraise of self, i.e. explaining how the UN is incapable to provide the aid that these countries need to rebuild their infrastructure of their societies to satisfy the educational purposes and other economical needs. The overstatement is of a huge importance, it describes the real situation of the affected countries and the lack of aid they suffers from.

Conclusions

The present study has reached to the following conclusions:

1. The role of maxims in the selected speeches of Theresa May is clear, since it has found that one paragraph can carry more than one maxim, and it is also an evident that other speeches might also be rich with maxims.
2. All the maxims have been used repeatedly, and every maxim used in many occasions and topics regarding what has been tackled during the speech.
3. The semantic innovation of Warrant's classification of the types of euphemism was the only category present within the analysis due to the gravity of expressions the other categories tackle within the text that the present of which is nearly impossible within the political sphere.

4. Regarding the rendition of the text from English into Arabic, the translator was governed by the static nature of the political text where no figurative tools were employed that left no space for creativity and ingenuity of the translator to take place in his work that led to literal translation.
5. Although the translator is considered the guardian of his language that did not stop him from conveying the exact meaning of what has been said that impinge his people and their cultural orientation.
6. The first hypothesis was proven to be correct for it is nearly impossible to achieve a 100% equivalent effect on the target reader due to the cultural differences and other previously mentioned reasons.

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